

Evaluation of an Irreversible Emergency Shutdown System for Fast Molten Salt Reactors in Maritime Applications Through Liquid Poison Injection

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ABSTRACT

Fast Molten Salt Reactors are one of the main advanced reactor designs being considered for maritime applications. For marine deployment, a shutdown system that is both rapid and irreversible is highly desirable for safety and security due to maritime unique scenarios such as piracy and sinking. This paper evaluates direct injection of a soluble neutron poison into the circulating NaCl-UCl₃ fuel as a candidate irreversible shutdown method. We build on a detailed two-dimensional, axisymmetric CFD model of the primary circuit in STAR-CCM+ to resolve buoyancy-driven flow, frictional losses in a porous-media heat exchanger, and passive-scalar transport of injected poisons. Time-dependent, spatially nonuniform poison fields are then transferred into an OpenMC model through a nine-region core segmentation to compute reactivity insertion versus time. Candidate poisons are screened for chemical compatibility, melting/boiling points, hazards, diffusion coefficients, and fast capture cross-sections; GdCl₃ and ⁶LiCl emerge as most promising. Simulations show the bottom cold-leg/core-inlet is the best injection location. At nominal power (180 MW_{th}), GdCl₃ achieves -2000 pcm within 15s at 0.1 bar and requires 186 kg for permanent shutdown; ⁶LiCl achieves -2000 pcm within 8s at 0.01 bar with 59 kg for permanent shutdown. At residual-heat conditions, reduced circulation increases both shutdown time and required mass, favouring lower injection pressures to limit total inventory. The results demonstrate feasibility of irreversible shutdown via poison injection, highlight design trade-offs among pressure, time, and inventory, and identify experimental and modelling needs for multi-species transport and 3-D effects. At 12.6 MW_{th} residual heat, GdCl₃ allows the core to reach -2000 pcm in under 39s at 0.01 bar and requires 200 kg of poison, while ⁶LiCl achieves the same reactivity insertion in 18.5s with 200 kg. At 1.8 MW_{th} an injection pressure of 0.01 bar achieves -2000 pcm within 82s and 38s for GdCl₃ and ⁶LiCl, respectively, requiring 546 kg of poison for permanent shutdown.

Keywords: molten chloride fast reactor, emergency shutdown, neutron poison injection, CFD-Monte Carlo coupling, maritime reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

The interest in civil nuclear maritime applications such as Floating Nuclear Power Plants and Nuclear Merchant Ships is seeing exponential growth globally due to aggressive decarbonization targets combined with coastal energy security needs. Advanced Molten Salt Reactor designs such as the Molten Chloride Fast Reactor (MCFR), led by TerraPower, are attractive due to low system pressure, high outlet temperature, ability to refuel online, and passive safety features [1][2].

The maritime environment presents unique conditions to be considered in design for both safety and security. From a safety perspective, marine accident end-states such as flooding and sinking bring up questions related to the criticality safety of the cold core under water moderation [3]. From a security by design standpoint, marine assets present potential threats such as hijacking (piracy) of the entire plant. For these reasons, an emergency shutdown mechanism that cannot be reversed with the equipment present at the plant is desirable in such designs.

Traditional molten salt safety concepts utilise fuel draining to a separate subcritical geometry through freeze plug or other valve systems. However, draining is much more challenging in the dynamic maritime environment, especially if gravity driven, and is relatively slow, reversible and vulnerable to

manual override. Direct absorber systems have been proposed for molten salt fast reactors, including gravity driven liquid absorber insertion, while literature on soluble poisons injected directly into liquid fuel remains limited [4][5]. Liquid poison injection in the moderator is a shutdown method utilised in both BWR and CANDU plants to deal with ATWS (Anticipated Transient Without Scram) scenarios. For MSRs, a soluble absorber distributed throughout the circulating fuel produces a long-lived reactivity penalty that cannot be removed without salt processing, which is advantageous for security and criticality safety considerations.

This paper presents a condensed version of a comprehensive screening of candidate poisons for NaCl-UCl₃ fuel [6]. Suitable poison candidates are utilised in a coupled CFD and Monte Carlo approach to quantify shutdown performance for soluble poisons in an MSR primary loop, with attention to injection location, pressure, and the mass required to keep the core subcritical. We also situate the work within recent PHYSOR contributions on MSR physics and tools, including data-driven incident detection for Molten Salt Fast Reactors (MSFRs), uncertainty quantification with open-source tools, quasi static kinetics for MSRs, and thermal MSR dynamics [7][8][9][10]. All reactor-specific inputs and findings summarized below originate from the dissertation accompanying this submission [6].

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Scope & Reactor Concept

A generic fast, chloride fuelled MSR is chosen for this evaluation based on existing literature. The fuel (salt) is chosen as NaCl-UCl₃, 54.1-45.9 mol percent, at about 948 K, with a core temperature rise near 100 K and total primary mass flow near 2600 kg s⁻¹.

This paper evaluates the feasibility of irreversible shutdown by soluble poison injection. Tasks include poison screening, CFD transport under nominal and residual heat powers, and time dependent neutronic impact via OpenMC with spatially heterogeneous poison fields.

The modelled core is a right circular cylinder with magnesium-oxide reflector, an annular downcomer, and a compact porous-media heat exchanger. The primary vessel is 304L stainless steel. Inner radius is of the order of tens of centimetres and active height is about one meter, consistent with maritime integration. A cover-gas plenum provides disengagement of fission gases. This geometry captures the buoyancy and pressure-loss balance that sets the loop circulation.

2.2. Poison Screening

Eight chlorides were considered: BCl₃, HfCl₄, EuCl₃, CdCl₂, SmCl₃, ErCl₃, LiCl, and GdCl₃. Screening criteria included melting and boiling points, chemical compatibility in chloride fuel, hazards, diffusion coefficients, fast spectrum absorption, and cost. BCl₃ and HfCl₄ are volatile at or near ambient or reactor conditions and EuCl₃ is strongly corrosive, so these were rejected. CdCl₂ presents acute toxicity and lower fast neutron absorption cross section. SmCl₃ and ErCl₃ melt above operating temperature and would require dilution, which would slow down reactivity insertion. LiCl and GdCl₃ best balance reactivity effects and practicality. Lithium must be enriched in ⁶Li for effectiveness, with tritium production as a consideration.

2.3. CFD Model

We use STAR-CCM+ with a 2D axisymmetric primary loop geometry that includes a hyperboloid like core vessel, a reflector block, and a porous-media heat exchanger region. The realizable k-ε two-layer model resolves turbulence near walls. Buoyancy is modelled with the Boussinesq approximation. A mesh independence study yielded a polyhedral mesh with a base cell size of 1 mm and 2.7×10⁵ cells. Heat addition in the core and removal in the exchanger are implemented as volumetric source and sink terms. Pressure drop in the exchanger agrees in order of magnitude with analytical correlations.

Operating points comprise 180 MW_{th} nominal heat and 12.6 MW_{th} (about 7%) and 1.8 MW_{th} (about 1%) residual heat loads. Steady state convergence criteria include residuals below 10⁻³, power balance within 1 percent, and the expected nominal core temperature rise of 106.5 K.

2.3.1. Poison transport

A passive scalar represents the poison mass fraction ϕ with molecular Schmidt numbers drawn from literature on diffusion coefficients of LiCl and GdCl₃ in molten-chloride salts. The turbulent Schmidt number is 0.9. Injection is modeled at several inlets as either unpressurized, Dirichlet on ϕ at the aperture, or pressurized mass flow inlet. Time integration uses an implicit unsteady scheme with $\Delta t = 0.1s$, based on a time-step independence study. Injection mass flows for pressure differentials of 0.01-10 bar follow orifice relations. The top opening serves as a salt-expansion outlet for pressurized cases.

2.4. Core Reactivity Modelling

To evaluate the changes in the reactivity of the core during poison injection, an OpenMC model is created based on the CFD results to perform k-eigenvalue simulations. Figure 1 represents a CSG-generated cylindrical core with nine fuel regions, reflecting the CFD segmentation and active core size. The cooling loop regions are omitted due to their negligible contribution to reactivity, as the flow of delayed neutron precursors is not accounted for in this study. The weight percent of the neutron poison in each core region is provided by the CFD simulations. This allows the computation of the weight percent of each nuclide in each core region for the OpenMC fuel material definition. Fresh fuel with no fission products is used as the most conservative case. Chlorine is set to nearly 100% ³⁷Cl enrichment, which is the most conservative assumption from a criticality safety perspective, due to the high absorption cross section of ³⁵Cl [5]. The nuclide cross-sections are taken from the ENDF/B-VIII.0 library. Based on the neutronic convergence study, the simulations are performed with 500,000 particles, 40 inactive batches, and 60 active batches [6]. Stochastic errors in the reactivity insertion estimates are within ± 20 pcm, which is acceptable considering the poison insertion reactivities of interest are of the order of 2000 pcm. Both the neutron spectrum and the neutron absorption reactions are tallied in the entire geometry to understand the effect of the candidate poisons.

Figure 1. OpenMC core geometry with 9 fuel salt regions. Fuel salt regions correspond to the nine inner regions, dark green represents the MgO reflector, and the outer light blue region represents the stainless steel 304L reactor vessel.

2.5. Study Limits

This study assesses shutdown performance using combined CFD transport and neutronics with heterogeneous poison fields at a constant temperature. Hardware architecture, actuation, and control logic are not analysed. Results are limited to the modelled geometry, power levels, injection locations, and pressure differentials reported here, and they reproduce the dissertation's findings. Temperature reactivity feedbacks are not accounted for, neither are the fuel-flow effects such as delayed neutron

precursors. Hyperboloid reactor core geometry is not modelled in OpenMC. Instead, a simpler cylindrical geometry is assumed. These limitations require further studies for the design implementation of the present shutdown method.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Steady Circulation & Flow Regime

At 180 MW_{th}, the loop maintains strong clockwise circulation. According to Figure 2, streamlines converge along the vertical core centreline, with small recirculation near the core inlet and the heat exchanger entrance. Mass flow decreases with power, about 2589 kg s⁻¹ at 180 MW_{th}, about 782 kg s⁻¹ at 12.6 MW_{th}, and about 300 kg s⁻¹ at 1.8 MW_{th}. These trends set the characteristic circulation times that govern inventory requirements for permanent shutdown.

Figure 2. Steady state velocity magnitude streamlines at 180 MW_{th}.

3.2. Injection Site Optimization

Because the Schmidt number is greater than one, momentum diffusion dominates mass diffusion. **As seen in Figure 3**, poison tends to follow streamlines, which creates heterogeneous core distributions that depend on the entry location.

Among the inlets tested, the bottom core inlet delivers higher concentrations to the reactivity sensitive centreline sooner than top or reflector inlets, which minimizes shutdown time, as shown in Figure 4.

According to Figure 4c, dual injection from the bottom inlet and the bottom reflector improves uniformity but is not required for a fast response.

Figure 3. Spatial and temporal evolution of neutron poison under 0.1 bar injection through the bottom inlet.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of neutron poison at 50s under 0.1 bar injection through various inlets.

3.3. Pressurized Versus Unpressurized Injection

The main requirement is to shut down the reactor by inserting -2000 pcm within a dozen seconds. According to Tables I and II, unpressurized injection barely exceeds about 100 ppm in the core after roughly 100s and would require on the order of one hour to approach -2000 pcm, which is too slow for emergency shutdown. Pressurization greatly accelerates delivery and mixing. At 10 bar pressure, the

core centreline concentration is about 45,000 ppm at 50s in the two-dimensional model. The mass required for a permanent shutdown is approximately the product of the injection mass flow and one loop circulation time. If injection stops early, poison is flushed out of the core into the downcomer, and reactivity can return to criticality.

3.4. Poison Choice, $GdCl_3$ versus 6LiCl

Under pressurized injection, shut down speed is relatively insensitive to plausible Schmidt number variations because advection dominates. The absorption strength in the fast spectrum is the main discriminator. Natural $LiCl$ is ineffective on the time scales of interest. Representative values at 180 MW_{th} for both $GdCl_3$ and 6LiCl are summarised in Tables I and II, respectively. $GdCl_3$ performs well but generally benefits from somewhat higher pressure for comparable speed, while enriched 6LiCl is highly effective at low pressure. Under pressurized injection, the shutdown time is always shorter than the time required for the neutron poison to complete a full loop circulation. Therefore, the mass required for a permanent shutdown, defined in the previous Section, is the same for both $GdCl_3$ and 6LiCl .

Table I. $GdCl_3$ bottom injection under nominal conditions.

ΔP (bar)	Shutdown time (s)	Reactivity insertion (pcm)	Mass of poison required (kg)
0.0	3600	-2036.8	219
0.01	35	-2149.4	58.8
0.1	15	-2216.2	186
1.0	8	-1997.3	587
10	5	-2129.6	1860

Table III. 6LiCl bottom injection under nominal conditions.

ΔP (bar)	Shutdown time (s)	Reactivity insertion (pcm)	Mass of poison required (kg)
0.0	734	-2362.7	22
0.01	8	-2085.8	58.8
0.1	6	-1983.7	186
1.0	4.5	-2265.4	587
10	3.5	-2148.3	1860

These values reflect injection mass flow scaling and circulation time in CFD. Tritium production with 6Li requires management. $GdCl_3$ avoids long-lived daughters and simplifies radiological controls. Both salts need moisture-free handling to avoid HCl formation and corrosion.

3.5. Residual-Heat Conditions

At 12.6 and 1.8 MW_{th} , slower circulation delays poison transport and increases the mass required for permanent shutdown, as reported in Tables III and IV, respectively. At 1.8 MW_{th} the poison reaches the upper part of the core in about 90s. Shutdown within roughly 90s to 2 minutes is acceptable at decay heat. At 1.8 MW_{th} , only the 0.01 bar case keeps the required inventory near 546 kg, while higher pressures raise it to about 1,726 kg at 0.1 bar, 5,455 kg at 1.0 bar, and 17,253 kg at 10 bar.

Table III. Residual heat 12.6 MW_{th}, bottom injection.

ΔP (bar)	GdCl ₃ shutdown time (s)	GdCl ₃ mass required (kg)	⁶ LiCl shutdown time (s)	⁶ LiCl mass required (kg)
0.01	39	200	18.5	200
0.1	30	632	13.5	632
1.0	15	1998	10.5	1998
10	11	6318	8.5	6318

Table IV. Residual heat 1.8 MW_{th}, bottom injection.

ΔP (bar)	GdCl ₃ shutdown time (s)	GdCl ₃ mass required (kg)	⁶ LiCl shutdown time (s)	⁶ LiCl mass required (kg)
0.01	82	546	38	546
0.1	45	1726	27	1726
1.0	28	5455	21.5	5455
10	20	17253	17	17253

3.6. Single-Failure Tolerance & Redundancy

A single bottom injector minimises time to subcriticality. A dual-line configuration, bottom plus bottom-reflector, reduces sensitivity to blockage or nozzle damage and improves cross-sectional coverage during the first circulation, at the expense of additional valves and heaters. This study assesses shutdown performance by developing heterogeneous poison fields with CFD and implementing them in OpenMC neutronics model. Hardware architecture, actuation, and control logic are not analysed. Results are limited to the modelled geometry, power levels, injection locations, and pressure differentials reported here, and they reproduce the dissertation's findings. A pragmatic allocation is a primary bottom line sized for the full-power target and a secondary bottom-reflector line sized for residual-heat hold-down and redundancy.

3.7. Materials Handling

Both candidate salts require dry systems to avoid HCl formation and associated alloy attack. Hygroscopic rare-earth chlorides call for inert-blanketed storage, heated-transfer lines, and desiccated cover gas. Selection of ⁶LiCl implies tritium production by ⁶Li(n, α), which requires cover-gas management and strict dryness consistent with chloride corrosion literature. GdCl₃ avoids long-lived radiological daughters but remains moisture sensitive. These provisions are consistent with chloride corrosion literature and with the conclusion that strict moisture control is mandatory.

4. DISCUSSION

A single bottom cold leg injector appears sufficient for rapid shutdown of a freshly fuelled fast MSR. A dual low-pressure configuration, bottom plus bottom reflector, can improve robustness against a single point failure, although the gain in speed is modest and must be weighed against added complexity. The mass required for permanence scales with loop circulation time, which argues for compact loop volumes and short holdup paths in the primary circuit. GdCl₃ and ⁶LiCl both offer viable shutdown performance but imply different system costs. GdCl₃ simplifies radiological controls and handling. ⁶LiCl enables very fast shutdown at lower pressures, thereby reducing the total mass of poison injected.

However, it requires enrichment and tritium management through cover gas control and getters. Both options require dry storage and injection trains designed for long-term quiescent service at temperature.

Modelling limits suggest clear next steps. The geometry is 2D and axisymmetric, which cannot capture pump swirl, bends, or ship motion. Density equality between poison and fuel was assumed for the passive scalar approach, so buoyancy driven segregation of poison towards the top or bottom regions of the core was neglected. This effect assumes importance under low core mass flow rates of residual heat mode. Therefore, future studies should aim at multi-species transport of poison through the fuel salt. Coupling of temperature-dependent reactivity feedback and accounting for flow of delayed neutron precursors would refine reactivity trajectories during cooldown. Further refinement of the neutronics model to better match the hyperboloid geometry will enhance accuracy of poison reactivity worth predictions.

CONCLUSION

Soluble neutron poison injection offers a credible path to irreversible emergency shutdown for fast Molten Salt Reactors. The bottom cold leg at the core inlet is the preferred location for speed. At full power, GdCl_3 provides about -2000 pcm reactivity insertion in about 15s at moderate pressure, while enriched $^6\text{LiCl}$ delivers similar performance at lower pressure and mass requirement, but with the trade-off of tritium management. Under residual heat conditions the approach remains viable, but design choices shift toward lower pressure to constrain inventory. The residual-heat tables quantify this shift, keeping shutdown within tens of seconds at $12.6 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$ and roughly 90s to 2 min at $1.8 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$ while holding inventory near 200 kg ($12.6 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) and 546 kg ($1.8 \text{ MW}_{\text{th}}$) at 0.01 bar. These findings support integrated design of the injection system, loop geometry, and storage capacity, followed by targeted experiments and higher fidelity Multiphysics simulations. The time scale of this shutdown method is relatively slow compared to modern RPS systems. In practical emergency procedures this liquid injection can be combined with control rod insertion, rendering the core irreversibly subcritical within a few seconds.

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